

DRIVER SLEEPINESS DETECTION USING CONVOLUTION NEURAL NETWORK

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Abstract – this article discusses the CNN model based on artificial intelligence. With this model, it is possible to define and develop a driver drowsiness detection system. The system will greatly help truckers, because dividing the driving of transport will lead to eye fatigue and the driver himself.

Keywords – CNN, model, computer vision, driver, system, artificial intelligence.

Annotatsiya - ushbu maqolada sun'iy intellektga asoslangan CNN modeli muhokama qilinadi. Ushbu model yordamida haydovchining uyquchanligini aniqlash tizimini aniqlash va ishlab chiqish mumkin. Tizim yuk tashuvchilarga katta yordam beradi, chunki transport nazoratini ajratish ko'z va haydovchining o'zini charchashiga olib keladi.

Kalit so'zlar - CNN, model, kompyuterni ko'rish, haydovchi, tizim, sun'iy intellekt.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, artificial intelligence is developing very quickly. Algorithms and models of artificial intelligence are already being used in all industries. The transport sector also uses smart traffic lights and cameras. Smart traffic lights apply to avoid traffic jams at the intersection. And smart cameras capture the violator of traffic and punches a fine by car number. With the help of computer vision, it is possible to develop many expert systems for different types, for example, a wagon number detection system, a driver's sleepiness detection system, a smart intersection, and many other expert systems [1].

Relevance. The system for detecting driver drowsiness using computer vision is very relevant today, because in many countries there are truckers and taxi drivers. Based on this analyzed system is very necessary for drivers to avoid accidents. In order to invigorate the driver, a certain system is needed, for example, if the driver started to doze off the investigated system should give a certain vibration, sound or splash a certain amount of water [2].

Goal. The system under study should work autonomously, follow the driver while driving the vehicle, that is, the entire route.

Tasks:

- Analyze the optimal model and algorithm;
- Develop software based on artificial intelligence and computer vision;
- Make a date set of the position of the head and the pupil of the eyes.

An image processing pipeline is a set of components commonly used between an image source (such as a camera, scanner, or imaging engine). in a computer game), and an image

renderer (such as a television, computer screen, computer printer, or movie screen), or for performing any intermediate digital image processing consisting of two or more separate processing units.

The image/video pipeline can be implemented as computer software, in a digital signal processor, on an FPGA, or as a fixed function ASIC. In addition, analog circuits can be used to perform many of the same functions.

Fig 1. Conveyor imaging.

Figure 1 shows a simplified, typical use of two imaging pipelines. The top half shows the components that can be found in a digital camera [3].

The lower half shows the components that can be used in an image viewer application on a computer to display images captured by the camera. (Note that operations that mimic physical, linear behavior, such as image scaling, are ideally performed on the left side, operating on linear RGB signals.

Operations that should look "perceptually uniform" such as lossy image compression on the other side of the hand should be done on the right side, working with "gamma corrected" r'g'b' or Y'CbCr signals.)

II. CNN MODEL ARCHITECTURE

Kernel convolution is not only used in CNNs, but is also a key element of many other Computer Vision algorithms. It is a process where

we take a small matrix of numbers (called kernel or filter), we pass it over our image and transform it based on the values from filter. Subsequent feature map values are calculated according to the following formula, where the input image is denoted by f and our kernel by h . The indexes of rows and columns of the result matrix are marked with m and n respectively.

After placing our filter over a selected pixel, we take each value from kernel and multiply them in pairs with corresponding values from the image. Finally, we sum up everything and put the result in the right place in the output feature map. Above we can see how such an operation looks like in micro scale, but what is even more interesting, is what we can achieve by performing it on a full image [5][6].

Valid and Same Convolution. As we have seen in when we perform convolution over the 6x6 image with a 3x3 kernel, we get a 4x4 feature map. This is because there are only 16 unique positions where we can place our filter inside this picture. Since our image shrinks every time we perform convolution, we can do it only a limited number of times, before our image disappears completely. What's more, if we look at how our kernel moves through the image we see that the impact of the pixels located on the outskirts is much smaller than those in the center of image. This way we lose some of the information contained in the picture. Below you can see how the position of the pixel changes its influence on the feature map [7],[8].

To solve both of these problems we can pad our image with an additional border. For example, if we use 1px padding, we increase the size of our photo to 8x8, so that output of the convolution with the 3x3 filter will be 6x6. Usually in practice we fill in additional padding with zeroes. Depending on whether we use padding or not, we are dealing with two types of convolutions — Valid and Same. Naming is quite unfortunate, so for the sake of clarity: Valid — means that we use the original image, Same — we use the border around it, so that the images at the input and output are the same size. In the second case, the padding width, should meet the following equation, where p is padding and f is the filter dimension (usually odd).

In previous examples, we always shifted our kernel by one pixel. However, step length can also be treated as one of convolution layer hyperparameters. When designing our CNN architecture, we can decide to increase the step if

we want the receptive fields to overlap less or if we want smaller spatial dimensions of our feature map. The dimensions of the output matrix - taking into account padding and stride - can be calculated using the following formula [9].

The transition to the third dimension. Convolution over volume is a very important concept, which will allow us not only to work with color images, but even more importantly to apply multiple filters within a single layer. The first important rule is that the filter and the image you want to apply it to, must have the same number of channels. Basically, we proceed very much like in the example, nevertheless this time we multiply the pairs of values from the three-dimensional space. If we want use multiple filters on the same image, we carry out the convolution for each of them separately, stack the results one on top of the other and combine them into a whole. The dimensions of the received tensor (as our 3D matrix can be called) meet the following equation, in which: n — image size, f — filter size, nc — number of channels in the image, p — used padding, s

— used stride, nf — number of filters.

Convolution Layers

The time has finally come to use everything we have learned today and to build a single layer of our CNN. Our methodology is almost identical to the one we used for densely connected neural networks, the only difference is that instead of using a simple matrix multiplication, this time we will use the convolution. Forward propagation consists of two steps. The first one is to calculate the intermediate value Z , which is obtained as a result of the convolution of the input data from the previous layer with W tensor (containing filters), and then adding bias b . The second is the application of a non-linear activation function to our intermediate value (our activation is denoted by g). Fans of matrix equations will find appropriate mathematical formulas below. If any of the operations in question is not clear to you, I highly recommend my previous article, in which I discuss in detail what is happening inside densely connected neural networks. By the way, on illustration below you can see a small visualization, describing the dimensions of tensors used in equation [10],[11].

Connections Cutting and Parameters Sharing At the beginning of the article I mentioned that densely connected neural networks are poor at

working with images, due to the huge number of parameters that would need to be learned. Now that we understand what convolution is all about, let's consider how it allows us to optimize the calculations. On the Figure below, the 2D convolution has been visualized in a slightly different way — neurons marked with numbers 1–9 form the input layer that receives brightness of subsequent pixels, while units A-D denotes calculated feature map elements. Last but not least, I-IV are the subsequent values from kernel — these must be learned.

Now, let's focus on the two very important attributes of convolution layers. First of all, you can see that not all neurons in the two consecutive layers are connected to each other. For example, unit 1 only affects the value of A. Secondly, we see that some neurons share the same weights. Both of these properties mean that we have much less parameters to learn. By the way, it is worth noting that a single value from the filter affects every element of the feature map — it will be crucial in the context of backpropagation [12],[13].

Convolutional Layer Backpropagation

Anyone who has ever tried to code their own neural network from scratch knows, that forward propagation is less than half the success. The real fun starts when you want to go back. Nowadays, we don't need to bother with backpropagation — deep learning frameworks do it for us, but I feel it's worth knowing what's going on under the hood. Just like in densely connected neural networks, our goal is to calculate derivatives and later use them to update the values of our parameters in a process called gradient descent.

In our calculations we will use a chain rule — which I mentioned in previous articles. We want to assess the influence of the change in the parameters on the resulting features map, and subsequently on the final result. Before we start to go into the details, let us agree on the mathematical notation that we will use — in order to make my life easier, I will abandon the full notation of the partial derivative in favour of the shortened one visible below. But remember, that when I use this notation, I will always mean the partial derivative of the cost function.

Our task is to calculate $dW[l]$ and $db[l]$ - which are derivatives associated with parameters of current layer, as well as the value of $dA[l-1]$ - which will be passed to the previous layer. As shown, we receive the $dA[l]$ as the input. Of

course, the dimensions of tensors dW and W , db and b as well as dA and A respectively are the same. The first step is to obtain the intermediate value $dZ[l]$ by applying a derivative of our activation function to our input tensor. According to the chain rule, the result of this operation will be used later.

Now, we need to deal with backward propagation of the convolution itself, and in order to achieve this goal we will utilise a matrix operation called full convolution — which is visualised below. Note that during this process we use the kernel, which we previously rotated by 180 degrees. This operation can be described by the following formula, where the filter is denoted by W , and $dZ[m,n]$ is a scalar that belongs to a partial derivative obtained from the previous layer.

Pooling Layers B. They are used primarily to reduce the size of the tensor and speed up calculations. These layers are simple - we need to divide our image into different regions, and then perform some operation for each of those parts. For example, for the Max Pool Layer, we select a maximum value from each region and put it in the corresponding place in the output. As in the case of the convolution layer, we have two hyperparameters available — filter size and stride. Last but not least, if you are performing pooling for a multi-channel image, the pooling for each channel should be done separately [14].

Pooling Layers Backpropagation. In this we will discuss only max pooling backpropagation, but the rules that we will learn — with minor adjustments — are applicable to all types of pooling layers. Since in layers of this type, we don't have any parameters that we would have to update, our task is only to distribute gradients appropriately. As we remember, in the forward propagation for max pooling, we select the maximum value from each region and transfer them to the next layer. It is therefore clear that during back propagation, the gradient should not affect elements of the matrix that were not included in the forward pass. In practice, this is achieved by creating a mask that remembers the position of the values used in the first phase, which we can later utilize to transfer the gradients [15].

III. RESULTS

During testing phase, we capture the video frames through camera and alert with an alarm when the model predicts drowsy output state continuously. Static images are used for training

but during testing phase key frames are extracted from continuous video and tested against the trained static images.

Fig 2. Normal state

Fig 3. After determining sleepiness

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V. CONCLUSION

In this scientific research and during the hackathon AI Challenge 2022, a ready-made software product was developed to determine driver sleepiness. Further scientific research will be dedicated to develop hardware complex to detect driver sleepiness.

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